

TREASURE

Policy brief 01

How EU legislation affects Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES)

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What is PTES?

Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) can provide large-scale, long-duration heat storage that **supports the integration of renewable energy**, district heating, and power-to-heat flexibility.

However, current EU electricity and heating market frameworks **do not fully recognise thermal energy storage as a distinct system asset**. Clarifying the regulatory treatment of PTES and enabling appropriate access to flexibility and support mechanisms are essential to unlock its full system value.

Why it matters

- Enables seasonal storage of renewable heat at significantly lower cost than electrochemical storage solutions.
- Reduces natural gas use in district heating and lowers peak electricity demand through power-to-heat shifting.
- Supports the achievement of EU 2030 and 2050 targets for renewable energy

Relevant EU legislation and policy levers (what currently matters)

1. Renewable Energy Directive (RED III) - Directive (EU) 2023/2413

Legal requirement

RED III defines renewable energy and waste heat (Article 2) and establishes binding national targets and annual increases for renewable energy in heating and cooling (Articles 15a and 23). Member States must calculate and report the share of renewable energy supplied for heating and cooling in accordance with these provisions.

Legal clarification

Heat supplied from pit thermal energy storage (PTES) can contribute to renewable heating and cooling targets only where the heat input originates from renewable energy sources or qualifies as waste heat, with detailed accounting methodologies determined at national level under RED III implementation.

Policy interpretation / gap

RED III does not explicitly address large-scale thermal energy storage technologies such as PTES, nor does it provide harmonised EU-level rules for the treatment of stored renewable heat, potentially leading to inconsistent recognition across Member States.

Relevant EU legislation and policy levers (what currently matters)

2. Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) - *Directive (EU) 2023/1791*

Legal requirement

The EED requires Member States to carry out comprehensive heating and cooling planning and assessments, including the identification of efficient district heating and cooling solutions and the integration of renewable energy and waste heat (Article 25). It also establishes criteria and obligations for efficient district heating and cooling systems (Article 26).

Legal clarification

While the EED recognises the role of waste heat recovery, renewables, and system efficiency, it does not explicitly mandate the consideration of long-duration or seasonal thermal energy storage within heating and cooling plans.

Policy interpretation / gap

As a result, technologies such as PTES risk being underrepresented in national and local planning processes, despite their potential to enhance decarbonisation, energy security, and operational flexibility in district heating systems.

Relevant EU legislation and policy levers (what currently matters)

3. Electricity Market Design (EMD) - *Electricity Regulation (EU) 2019/943 and Electricity Directive (EU) 2019/944, as amended*

Legal requirement

The EU electricity market framework promotes system flexibility and enables eligible assets such as electricity storage and demand-side response to participate in ancillary services and capacity mechanisms, subject to national implementation and market rules.

Legal clarification

Large-scale thermal energy storage technologies, including PTES, are not explicitly addressed or classified within the Electricity Market Design framework, as they are primarily heat-sector assets rather than electricity storage.

Policy interpretation / gap

This lack of explicit recognition may limit the ability of PTES to access electricity-market-related revenue streams linked to flexibility provision, even where PTES deployment can reduce peak electricity demand, enable renewable electricity integration, and support overall system stability.

Relevant EU legislation and policy levers (what currently matters)

4. REPowerEU

Legal requirement

REPowerEU does not constitute binding EU legislation and does not introduce new legal obligations for Member States with respect to heat planning, district heating, or thermal energy storage. Its provisions are implemented primarily through amendments to national Recovery and Resilience Plans and related funding instruments.

Legal clarification

While REPowerEU includes measures to accelerate renewable energy deployment, energy savings, and infrastructure investments, it does not establish specific regulatory definitions or eligibility criteria for thermal energy storage technologies, including pit thermal energy storage (PTES).

Policy interpretation / gap

By prioritising rapid renewable heat deployment and energy security objectives, particularly the reduction of dependence on Russian fossil fuel imports, REPowerEU creates favourable conditions for the deployment of large-scale thermal energy storage such as PTES. However, the absence of explicit references to thermal storage means that support for PTES remains indirect and dependent on national implementation choices and funding priorities.

Potential impacts on key stakeholders

District heating operators

District heating operators could benefit from lower system-level heat generation costs and improved integration of renewable and waste heat sources through the use of PTES. At the same time, adjustments to tariff structures and cost-allocation rules may be required to reflect the capital-intensive nature of large-scale thermal storage and its system benefits.

Municipalities and regions

Municipalities and regional authorities could use PTES as a strategic tool to support the decarbonisation of local heating systems and to meet climate and energy targets, particularly in areas with existing or planned district heating networks.

Electricity transmission and distribution system operators (TSOs/DSOs)

By enabling sector coupling and shifting heat demand away from peak electricity periods, PTES can contribute to system flexibility and help reduce winter peak loads. This may ease grid congestion and lower the need for network reinforcements, benefiting both TSOs and DSOs.

Potential impacts on key stakeholders

Investors and utilities

Investors and utilities would benefit from greater regulatory clarity on the treatment of thermal energy storage and improved access to relevant funding and market mechanisms. Clear and predictable frameworks are essential to support financing decisions and the large upfront investments required for PTES deployment.

Consumers

End consumers could benefit from more stable and predictable heat prices over time, as well as reduced exposure to fossil fuel price volatility and lower dependence on imported natural gas.

